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V1.0	02/06/2025	Final Draft further to Independent EAB Members' and AIDAVA EAB

¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

- R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

- PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

		Members' review and contributions

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List of Definitions

The definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary [[ref](#)].

Executive Summary

This Deliverable D4.9 provides the second report of AIDAVA's Ethics Advisory Board of Independent Experts (EAB). It summarises the main activities of the EAB and provides details of current and next steps in ethics oversight of AIDAVA throughout 2024 and 2025.

Throughout 2024 and 2025 the EAB had provided advisory on the implementation of G1 and planning for G2. For G1 the EAB attended an in person Workshop in Maastricht with Patient Consultants to prepare for evaluations throughout Summer 2024. The EAB also provided input on the results presented in the G1 Report.

For G2 the EAB liaised closely with the Patient Advisory Board and Sustainability Board, providing input to the Consent Forms, Study Information Packages as well as amendments to the ethics approvals for G1 to support Developer Access to raw data for their implementation and validation work.

The EAB advice remains focused on ensuring that the participant's voice is heard clearly and that due consideration is given to their experience and feedback in participating in AIDAVA. They have explored other areas of relevance, including the role of synthetic data in testing and validation and with a wider view of the implications of newer regulations (including the AI Act and EHDS) on AIDAVA.

As the project approaches the last year of its operation the EAB will focus on ethics issues associated with the execution of G2 and future plans for AIDAVA, particularly on the patient experience and user-friendliness of the App. They will continue to work closely with the Patient and Sustainability Advisory Boards. The EAB will continue to balance the advisory scope of their intervention role with the unique and hands-on approach they have taken in engaging with the project, its development and regulatory teams, fellow Advisory Boards and the Patient Consultants.

1 Introduction

This Deliverable D4.9 provides the second report of AIDAVA’s Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) of experts. It has been drafted in partnership between the external experts and AIDAVA’s internal team members from WP1 and WP4. It provides a summary of the main activities throughout 2024 and 2025 after the EAB was established in September 2023. This report discusses the EAB’s activities, oversight of the Project and its contributions.

Further to its constitution in 2023 and the replacement of Birgid Bauer by Julie Power as described in D4.5. The EAB had an additional change in 2024 for its AIDAVA internal members, where Kerli Norlak stood down from her position and was replaced by Mall Maasik to represent WP1 for AIDAVA. The EAB sent their best wishes to Kerli, and welcomed Mall to the Board.

The EAB is therefore constituted as follows:

External members	Role and Background
Brendan Barnes	Regulatory Expert and Former Privacy Officer for EFPIA (retired)
Julie Power	Patient Representative - Patient Contact and Policy Officer for Vasculitis Ireland Awareness (commencing March 2024)
Peter Singleton	Regulatory Expert and Director Cambridge Health Informatics
Don Willison	AIDAVA EAB Chair, Public Health and Governance Expert, Faculty Member, University of Toronto
Sofia Palmieri (observer)	Observer and PhD Candidate.
Internal Members	
Dipak Kalra	WP4 Lead
Nathan Lea	Task 4.1 Lead
Isabelle de Zegher	Clinical Lead and co-coordinator
Mall Maasik	WP1 Lead
Gabrijela Radic	Project management Office

The Running Minutes of the EAB remain available on request.

2 Description of Activities

This section describes the activities of the EAB throughout 2024 and to date in 2025.

2.1 Meetings and Operation

Throughout 2024, there was significant EAB activity to:

- help address the finalisation of the G1 assessments,
- assist with the review of the outcomes published in the G1 report,
- provide input to the development of the G2 assessment, protocol, information leaflets, consent and participant involvement particulars, and the amendments to the ethics approvals at each site
- Advise and guide future plans and developments, addressing themes including digital equity and understanding the roles and responsibilities of HDIs in real world deployment.

These issues were addressed both through several virtual and two in-person meetings. In the course of addressing some of these issues, the EAB collaborated with the Patient Advisory Board.

The EAB has continued to meet roughly quarterly throughout 2024 and 2025. Since the first report, there have been meetings held on 14th May 2024, 1st August 2024, 14th October 2024, 14th November 2024 and 4th March 2024. There has also been one ad hoc meeting to address points that had been raised and discussed via email throughout September 2024, with an ad hoc meeting held on 8th November 2024 and significant discussion via email around key points as outlined in section 3.

Additionally the EAB Chair, Don Willison, has continued to meet with the WP4 i~HD Lead, Nathan Lea, more frequently to be apprised of issues raised and addressed by the Board as the project advanced and reached its G1 study execution point. Until the end of 2024, they would meet roughly fortnightly or when there were any pressing matters to attend to. From 2025, the meeting frequency has been reduced to every four to six weeks on the basis that the G2 protocol and submissions for ethics committee amendments had a deadline of February 2025 and the EAB focus has shifted away from more operational matters to those around the oversight of G2 and the monitoring of changing legislative requirements.

2.2 In Person Meetings

EAB External Members have had the opportunity to join AIDAVA in two in-person meetings in 2024. The first was the AIDAVA Pilot Maastricht workshop attended by Don Willison and Brendan Barnes on 14th May 2024. The EAB members present were able to meet development, HDI and programme management teams, as well as the Patient Consultants in an attempt to understand the project at an operational level and the proposed assessment methods. This was in line with the details provided in the first EAB report as published in D4.5.

Don Willison, Peter Singleton and Brendan Barnes were also able to join the consortium meeting in Tallinn on 14th November 2024 to further participate in the planning and development of the G2 assessments and to provide feedback about the EAB and its activities to date, as well as focus on the key points of consideration as outlined in Section 3.

3 Activities and Outputs Discussion

3.1 Key Points of Focus for the EAB

The EAB covered activities related to G1 and G2 as AIDAVA progressed across the two milestones. The advisory and guidance below has been considered throughout the management of the project, including the results of the G1 prototype and report as well as the specific points for amendment.

3.1.1 G1 Assessment and Report Feedback, G2 Advisory

The EAB have continued to focus on the participant experience and wider patient and public voice in the current period. This included a review of the G1 report where they felt that there was a need for clearer communication in G2 with potential and enrolled study participants regarding the purpose of the study, as there seemed to be poor understanding and possibly unrealistic expectations. The EAB recommended that G2 should ask fewer, clearer questions of study participants and have a clean knowledge graph, to facilitate development of a clean International Patient Summary (IPS).

The EAB also provided advice for the G2 preparations, including recommendations for revisions to the updated Study Information Packages (SIP) and Informed Consent Forms (ICF). On these, the EAB specifically discussed the need for a single template for the sites to adapt to their setting, not two. There should also be a focus on plain language and shorter length for the materials to aid accessibility and understanding. There was also an expectation from the EAB that it must be clear that there is no direct benefit to study participants from participating in the study.

The EAB also recommended that research staff at participating sites should go beyond documenting the answers to the EAB's specific questions. Specifically, they recommended that staff document, in separate notes, observations about the process surrounding the interactions and research participant responses at time of recruitment and any time there is a direct encounter with research participants. This is particularly important as this is a proof-of-concept study, and this could provide valuable learning.

Though valued and well received, AIDAVA partners opted not to amend the proposed amendments and protocols for the resubmission for Independent Research Ethics Committee / Review Board approvals. As described at the EAB Meeting on 27th May 2025, this was due to the difficulty in managing the workload for amendments that went above and beyond the evaluations described in the initial proposal and approvals. The EAB noted that it would be optimal for it to have commenced its work sooner in the project, perhaps with appointments being made earlier in the first year and more time to get actively involved in advising on the project during Year 1.

The EAB also heard that it is difficult to ensure consistency across different partner sites in terms of the informed consent procedure and provision of SIPs across multiple sites spanning multiple national jurisdictions, each of which require translation into local language and adherence to local protocols. All materials that had been submitted would need to meet the standards locally for ensuring the participants understood the benefit that they may receive (or lack thereof), and this would be independently assessed by the Review Boards in each site.

3.1.2 Approvals and Consents Update - Developer Access to Raw Data and Synthetic Data Use proposals for G2

One aspect of the assessments for G1 was the discovery that all developers would need to access identifiable information to validate the AI components and the system operation. GND had been the only partner who was specifically named in the original consent forms. This would become problematic for G2 where the other AIDAVA developer partners would also need access.

The EAB advised on how the consent form wording might be updated to ensure that developer partners could get the access they needed. The EAB also assisted in the development of a proposal to commence synthetic data development in case access could not be granted to real identifiable data.

Peter Singleton noted in respect of synthetic data:

- We need to be clear what ‘synthetic data’ (SD) is needed as it will change what ‘real’ data is used and what algorithms might be applied
- Is the SD for ‘volume testing’ or is high-fidelity SD required?
- SD can create more records, but can’t actually create more ‘information’

Grateful for Peter Singleton’s advice, AIDAVA has decided not to take a computationally derived SD approach since the last round of feedback provided by the EAB. An engineering solution has been used to help provide approaches to ensure that there is available data to test the system features where needed (i.e. manually created data with ‘Sunny’ parts (where data processing is as expected in an ideal scenario) and ‘Stormy’ parts (where errors occur in data handling in a more realistic scenario)).

3.1.3 Post Project Considerations - Digital Equity

On consideration of the G1 report and wider discussion the current form of AIDAVA is likely of interest to only 5% of the population. The EAB is keen that approaches are found to address how AIDAVA could appeal to a broader group of the public in the longer term. The EAB recommended a working group separate from the EAB but with participation from EAB members. There has been interest expressed in this but it is likely that this recommendation will be deferred until there is a better understanding of the AIDAVA solution’s impact.

3.1.4 HDI Roles and Responsibilities

The EAB has also considered the role of HDIs in the general scheme of health data management and citizen experience. The initial discussions started to establish a foundation for the work on Deliverable 4.12 - Proposed operating model for HDI. In the coming year the EAB may re-visit this, as required, picking up the key points learned from the compliance requirements as outlined in D4.8 as described below.

3.2 Advisory Board Engagement

In the current period, the EAB has engaged with the Patient Advisory Board (PAB) and Sustainability Advisory Board (SAB). These included in person meetings at the Annual General Meeting and online meetings.

The key themes addressed included how best the EAB can support sustainability activity for AIDAVA with a focus on the digital equity issue described in 3.1.3 above, as well as collaborating with the PAB on the development of the SIP and ICF. PAB representatives have been invited to join the EAB meetings to gather insights and updates on how the EAB operates and the key themes that are of focus so that they can work better together on the project and its outputs.

3.3 Forthcoming EAB Oversight and Reviews

3.3.1 Changing Regulatory Landscape

The EAB will continue to monitor the changing regulatory landscape. This will be further to the update briefing they received on the evolving regulations in the October 2024 meeting from WP4 leads at the Annual General Meeting. The Deliverable offered a view of the key legislation that would impact the development and deployment of the AIDAVA solution, where the EAB will offer their inputs as those

key legislative instruments are adopted over the coming two years. Whilst AIDAVA will have completed by the time the pertinent elements of the AI Act will come into force, it is likely that AIDAVA will be considered a high risk system and medical device (or less likely an accessory to medical devices). The EAB will continue to monitor this and the implications of the AI Act as it is introduced. This will help to update the specifications for potential trials and product development after AIDAVA has completed.

The EAB will also continue to support the G2 as it is conducted and offer inputs and points. Part of the EAB's feedback during G1 and for G2 was to encourage AIDAVA to explore the patient and participant experience in more detail. To date, patient experience has been captured primarily through the usability survey. Nurse and curator experience of interacting with patients has also been captured. These inputs have been important in framing a realistic assessment of the G1 tool, a difficult but important project output. Collaborative data-cleaning has proved more technically challenging than expected, but the levels of continuing patient participation suggest recognition of the value of the project from the patient perspective. It is recognised that AIDAVA's project scope did not, at initiation, include a more in-depth examination of patient experience and that this is not something that can be engineered into the project at this stage. At the same time, informal exchanges in the margins of AIDAVA meetings indicate that insights are available which could inform future projects. Depending on resources, this point may be more applicable, when results from G2 can inform how to better probe these areas in more detail and potentially for any further work and sustainability activity.

With the activities that are being planned, the EAB has scope for potentially one last in-person meeting before the end of the project. This will likely coincide with the project plenary schedule and will focus on understanding the latest developments with the G2 evaluations and further input into post project work and sustainability goals.

The EAB will continue to meet virtually roughly every three to four months as needed. The Chair will also meet with WP4 representatives roughly every six weeks, increasing should the need arise as G2 advances and the regulatory landscape shifts require particular attention from the EAB.

3.3.2 Next Steps

The EAB will continue to oversee the key points of consideration outlined throughout this section. Plenary meetings will continue, likely one per quarter over the coming fifteen months. In Person Attendance in Split for Autumn 2025 will be considered in the coming period, with a decision likely in August.

Throughout this period the EAB will be kept up to date with ongoing developments as G2 proceeds over the coming months. The Chair and T4.1 lead will meet every six weeks as currently scheduled.

4 Conclusion

2024 to 2025 has been a significant period for AIDAVA: not only has it completed its prototyping under G1, it has also assessed the learning from the prototype and commenced with G2 for a full functionality review. During this period, the EAB has been able to directly advise on the learning outcomes as well as the planning for the next evaluations.

The EAB has provided key recommendations on the execution of G2 and the interpretation of participant feedback from G1, where these focused primarily on better understanding of the participant experience. This focus is evolving for the EAB to understand the benefit and desirability of the AIDAVA solution.

The EAB and Project recognise the practical, involved and hands on approach by the EAB, and AIDAVA Stakeholders are very grateful for this. The EAB also recognises that it walks a fine line in terms of having an advisory role but also being concerned with ensuring their recommendations have a meaningful and lasting impact on the project from a practical perspective.

Whilst the scope of an advisory board will be limited to offering advice, the EAB has still recognised that getting started earlier in the project lifecycle would certainly be beneficial for setting the initial course in addition to offering course corrections in the planning of studies earlier on in their development.

With these learning points in mind, the EAB will continue to work on its guidance and focus areas throughout the rest of 2025 and until the project conclusion in 2026. A further report will be published in mid-2026.

5 Annexes

5.1 EAB Running Minutes

Available on request.